

Contrast enhancement using Wiener and Mean filters combined with CLAHE in dense breast images

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Abstract—In Brazil, the breast cancer is the most frequent malignant tumor with an estimated risk of 53.33 cases per 100,000 women. New technologies have been studied and developed to facilitate early diagnosis. However, mammography is still the main resource for screening, directly influencing the possibility of cure of the disease. Digital image processing appears as an additional tool to assist radiologists in mammogram assessments. The goal of this work is to evaluate the Wiener and Mean Filters with Contrast-limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) technique. We used 127 images divided into classes 'c' and 'd' of breast densities (dense breasts), those with a higher risk of developing breast cancer, mainly due to the greater difficulty of diagnosis. For the quantitative results, we calculated the Measure of Enhancement (EME) and the Mean Structural Similarity Index (MSSIM). The results showed that for processing methods increased the EME values, indicating an increase in the contrast of the images in relation to the original ones. In addition, the EME values for the 'd' class images, the densest class, were smaller, which proves that these images have lower contrast compared to the images from class 'c', due to the higher presence of fibroglandular tissue. The MSSIM values were very similar for all processing, which can also be proved by visual analysis. We concluded that it was possible through the use of filters and CLAHE to increase the contrast of the resulting images in dense mammographic images.

Keywords— breast cancer, contrast enhancement, digital filtering, mammography.

I. INTRODUCTION

The American Cancer Society estimates, each year, the number of new cases of cancer (incidence), survival and mortality rate in the United States. For this country, more than 270,000 new cases of breast cancer are estimated in 2019, corresponding to 30% of cancer cases in women [1]. In Brazil, the numbers are no different. Overall, excluding non-melanoma skin cancers, breast cancer is the most frequent malignant tumor among Brazilian women. More than 59,000 new cases are estimated this year, with an estimated risk of 53.33 cases per 100,000 women [2].

Mammography exam is still the method indicated for routine screening of women's integral health care. This exam becomes essential, since it is the main modality for screening that allows early diagnosis, directly influencing the mortality rate, and especially the possibility of cure of the disease [3-4].

However, the quality of the mammographic image is of utmost importance for the correct diagnosis of the radiologist [5-6]. In case the equipment is not calibrated, generating a low image quality, the high presence of quantum noise in the images influences the contrast, being able to cause problems during the assessment and fine-detail tasks, such as the

discrimination between benign and malignant masses, as well as the detection of very small structures, like microcalcifications [7].

In recent years, aiming increasingly at the early detection of breast cancer, notably in dense breasts (predominance of fibroglandular tissue), a promising new technique for digital imaging has emerged: digital breast tomosynthesis (DBT) [8]. Nonetheless, this new technique in that results in images of breast projections/slices is still far from the Brazilian breast cancer screening reality (in most imaging facilities), besides being an additional exam to mammography.

Thus, digital image processing becomes crucial and emerge as a tool for noise filtering, as well as contrast enhancement, aiding specialists in detecting suspicious mammographic findings and lesions [9]. Although each manufacturer develops their own image processing method in their equipment, researchers have been developing and studying various algorithms for use in mammographic images [10-15]. It is important to propose a combination of filter and contrast enhancement, since if the noise is not filtered, it can also be enhanced along with the signal by using only the contrast enhancement technique.

The goal of this work is to evaluate the Wiener and Mean Filters with a contrast enhancement technique (CLAHE) based on adaptive histogram equalization in 127 dense breast mammographic images. For the quantitative results, we calculated the Measure of Enhancement (EME) and the Mean Structural Similarity Index (MSSIM).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Image database

We used 127 mammographic images from INbreast digital database [16]. Of these 127 images, 99 belong to the class 'c' of BI-RADSTM [17] breast density, indicating heterogeneously dense breasts. The other 28 images were assessed as belonging to pattern 'd' of breast density, i. e., the densest class, when the breasts are composed almost entirely of fibroglandular tissue. These breast types are considered to have a higher risk of breast cancer, due to the greater diagnostic difficulty [18], proving the importance of studies in dense breasts.

Each fully anonymized image contains an individual assessment made by specialists, containing the medical information of the images, including the breast density. The mammograms were acquired using a full-field digital mammography, processed and evaluated in DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) format, with 12-bit contrast resolution, size of 2560 x 3328 or 3328 x 4084 pixels in both views: craniocaudal (CC) and mediolateral oblique (MLO).

B. Digital filters: Wiener and Mean

The first filter used in the images was the Wiener filter. This filter is a low pass adaptive for denoising that aims to smooth out the noise that may corrupt the signal. It is known as “Minimum Mean Square Error Filtering”, it minimizes the mean square error between the estimated random process and the reference (desired) process. Establishing the power spectrum of the original image and the noisy image, the technique considers the effects of noise and seeks to minimize the difference between the restored image and the original one [19].

The other filter used was the Mean filter. Like the Wiener, it also consists of a low-pass filter whose effect on the image is smoothing and noise minimization since it eliminates or attenuates the high frequency components present in the image. However, this process may blur the image and thus fine details may be lost [9].

This filter consists of exchanging the central pixel value of a processing kernel (window) by the arithmetic average of the pixel values contained in this window. The calculation of the Mean filter is shown in (1),

$$g(x, y) = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{(s,t) \in S_{xy}} f(s, t) \quad (1)$$

where, $g(x,y)$ is the output pixel of the filtered image, S_{xy} represents the set of coordinates in the rectangular window of size $m \times n$, and $f(s,t)$ is the original image pixel value. Both for Wiener and Mean filter, the kernel size (m,n) used was 3×3 .

C. Contrast-limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE)

The Contrast-limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) was developed by Pizer and colleagues [20] as being a variation of a histogram equalization. It is used for contrast enhancement, since the original image histogram is adjusted in a new predefined histogram, where the exceeding values are redistributed to other intensities based on a clip-limit and a distribution function.

The CLAHE technique is effective in contrast enhancement, however it is important to apply such technique after the noise filtering step, thus avoiding also enhancing noisy signal [21]. In the CLAHE algorithm, the user has to set some parameters, such as: window size, clip-limit and probability distribution function. So, in this work, after experimental tests, we set a 15×15 pixels window size (image subdivision), clip-limit equal to 0.01, and a uniform probability distribution function. In short, we generated three different resultant images from the original ones: Wiener filter + CLAHE, Mean Filter + CLAHE, and only with CLAHE.

D. Quantitative measures: measure of enhancement (EME) and Mean Structural SIMilarity Index (MSSIM)

In order to quantitatively measure the contrast promoted by CLAHE, we calculated the measure of enhancement (EME) proposed by Agaian and researchers [22]. This metric aims to validate the contrast in an objective way, since it takes into account that an image's processed pixels have a strong dependence on the surrounding pixels. EME is defined by the equation presented in (2),

$$EME = \max_{\Phi \in \{\Phi\}} x \left(\frac{1}{k_1 k_2} \sum_{l=1}^{k_2} \sum_{k=1}^{k_1} 20 \log \frac{I_{max;k,l}^w}{I_{min;k,l}^w} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, $I_{max;k,l}^w$ and $I_{min;k,l}^w$ are the maximum and minimum of the the image $X(n,m)$, respectively inside the block $w_{k,l}$. The image should be split into $k_1 k_2$ blocks $w_{k,l}(i,j)$ of sizes $l_1 \times l_2$.

The region of interest (ROI) segmentation for EME calculation, was made from the following methodology: we calculated the center pixel of the image, by dividing by 2 the number of rows and columns of the image; after that, the center pixel was shifted in 1000 to 500 columns left (-1000 to -500) or right (+500 to +1000) (depending on breast laterality) and in 250 rows up and down, generating a 500×500 pixels ROI. This methodology is exemplified in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Example of an image used in this work, as well as how the region of interest (ROI) was cropped for EME calculation. The red dot roughly shows the image center pixel location, based on the total number of rows and columns in the image. If the breast laterality were not this, the ROI is shifted to to the other side (right) from the center pixel.

The Structural Similarity (SSIM) index was other metric used in order to evaluate the similarity between two images. This technique breaks down the signal into three components: two real numbers that evaluate the overall brightness and contrast of the image, and a normalized image that contains only structural information [23].

This measure of similarity between a pair of images is calculated in several image windows and may vary the function and size of this window. The SSIM calculation two windows (same size) of coordinates x and y is shown in (3),

$$SSIM(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x \mu_y + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)} \quad (3)$$

where, μ_x e μ_y are the average of the coordinates x and y , C_1 and C_2 are constants, σ_x and σ_y are the variance of (x,y) , and σ_{xy} represents the x and y covariance.

In practice, it is important to obtain an overall image quality measure. Therefore, the Mean Structural Similarity (MSSIM) is calculated through the arithmetic mean of the individual values obtained in each window, resulting in a single and global SSIM value for the pair of images analyzed. MSSIM ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates that the pair of images analyzed is identical.

The results were generated by dividing the images between the classes ‘c’ and ‘d’ of breast density. For this, the mean and standard deviation of both EME and MSSIM were calculated for each image processing. Fig. 2 shows a block diagram summarizing the methodology applied in this work.

Fig. 2. Block diagram summarizing the methodology.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table I presents the average results obtained for the EME by cropping the region of interest (500 x 500 pixels) of the original images and the processed ones.

TABLE I. EME: AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION FOR CLASS 'C' AND 'D' OF BREAST DENSITY.

Images	Measure of enhancement (EME)			
	Original	Wiener + CLAHE	Mean + CLAHE	CLAHE
Class 'c'	1.24 ± 0.31	6.23 ± 1,20	5.01 ± 0.93	7.93 ± 1.59
Class 'd'	1.17 ± 0.16	6.07 ± 1,15	4.81 ± 0.84	7.43 ± 1.44

The original images presented an average EME value of 1.24 and 1.17, for images of classes 'c' and 'd', respectively. From the results of Table I, it can be inferred that the application of the CLAHE contrast enhancement technique promoted an increase in EME values for all processing when compared to the original image. These results were expected, since the objective of this technique is to increase the image contrast, allowing greater differentiation between the image structures.

Another issue to discuss is whether the greatest results were obtained when applying only the CLAHE technique, with EME equal to 7.93 and 7.43, for classes 'c' and 'd', respectively. As in these images there was no application of any filter for denoising, there was no smoothing of the image, which allowed a greater increase of contrast. However, it is noteworthy that in this case, the noise present in the original image were also highlighted, since there was no previously signal filtering.

When comparing the processing with the Wiener filter + CLAHE and the Mean filter + CLAHE, it appears that the Mean filter obtained lower EME values than for the Wiener filter. In theory, this was expected since the Mean filter causes a higher level of blur in the image compared to the Wiener filter, thus decreasing the contrast after CLAHE processing.

Analyzing the calculations for the different breast densities classes, it is observed that the values of EME for the class "d" were always smaller than for the class "c". This is explained by the fact that images of the denser pattern (class 'd') of breast density noticeably show lower contrast, due to the greater predominance of fibroglandular tissue, making it difficult to differentiate structures. Thus, the contrast in images of this pattern generally has lower contrast than in images of the 'c' pattern.

Fig 3. shows an example of cropped regions of interest used for EME calculation, and also for visual analysis. A priori, there is a significant visual difference between the original and the processed ones. However, the processed images are very similar to each other.

Fig. 3. Regions of interest obtained from the following images: (A) Original image; (B) Original image + Wiener filter + CLAHE; (C) Original image + Mean filter + CLAHE; (D) Original image + CLAHE.

Table II shows the results for the MSSIM calculated between the original image and the resulting images after each processing applied. Note that the closer to 1, the more similar the compared images are.

TABLE II. MSSIM: AVERAGE AND STANDARD DEVIATION FOR CLASS 'C' AND 'D' OF BREAST DENSITY.

Images	Mean Structural Similarity Index (MSSIM)		
	Wiener + CLAHE	Mean + CLAHE	CLAHE
Class 'c'	0.838 ± 0.055	0.833 ± 0.056	0.841 ± 0.052
Class 'd'	0.860 ± 0.047	0.854 ± 0.048	0.864 ± 0.045

From Table II, the highest values of MSSIM found, as well as with the EME, were for processing with CLAHE. However, it is possible to verify the similarity between the MSSIM values obtained for the three applied processing, indicating that the resulting images are very similar in luminance level and structure between them. This is clearly observed in Fig.3, in which, visually, the images are very similar. Fig 4. exhibits an example of one original image used in the work, as well as each of the processing methods, such as: Wiener filter + CLAHE, Mean filter + CLAHE and only CLAHE.

Fig. 4. (A) Original image; (B) Original image + Wiener filter + CLAHE; (C) Original image + Mean filter + CLAHE; (D) Original image + CLAHE.

By MSSIM, there is no significant difference between the application of filters and CLAHE, contrary to what was shown in EME (Table I). It is certainly CLAHE that promotes this drop in MSSIM values compared with the original images, since if you apply only filters without contrast enhancement, the MSSIM values are very close to the original image, because there is not so much change in contrast and luminance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Breast cancer is considered a public health problem worldwide. In addition, the quality of the equipment, the complexity of mammographic images and the subjectivity in image assessment may difficult early detection of this disease. Thus, from this work it was possible to propose a combination of filter with an adaptive histogram equalization technique (Wiener filter + CLAHE) that promoted increased contrast in dense mammographic images, both visually and by means of quantitative EME measurement.

As future steps, it is suggested the application of new filters for noise smoothing and other techniques for contrast enhancement as a comparison with the results obtained in this work. In addition, we should expand our database with images from different equipment.

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